

A NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF DYNAMIC TRANSVERSE SHEAR FAILURE

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SUMMARY: A dynamic test to determine the high strain rate transverse shear strength of a composite has been investigated by finite element analysis. The failure prediction using a solid element based numerical model is severely influenced by the mesh density when stress singularities exist at the failure position. The introduction of zero-thickness interface elements between potential failure planes of the model effectively eliminates the mesh dependency problems. The baseline interface element based model still predicts failure at a lower failure stress than the experimental result. The differences are interpreted as being due to the influence of compressive stresses on the delamination threshold at the failure initiation points. A set of modified failure initiation and propagation criteria are proposed for the interface elements to take the influence of compression on matrix shear strength and G_{IIC} into account.

KEYWORDS: Interface elements, mesh sensitivity, failure criteria, interlaminar shear

INTRODUCTION

The through thickness properties of composite materials are typically lower than the in-plane properties and represent a weakness and potential failure mechanism, particularly in impact loading scenarios. It is therefore important to be able to characterise these properties and have numerical models to predict failure. Dong and Harding¹ developed a single-lap shear specimen for use at high strain rate to characterise the through-thickness shear strength of carbon/epoxy laminates. This strength was used as an input parameter into a finite element model to predict the delamination failure but it was found that local stress concentrations caused differences between the test result and the finite element predictions². As a result of this highly localised stress concentration results are further dependent on the mesh refinement in the area of high stress gradients

A new method for predicting delamination failure based on interface elements has been developed and implemented in the explicit code LS-Dyna³. This avoids the problem of the local stress concentration since failure is located at the interface between plies and yielding occurs once a critical stress has been reached. Analyses of the single lap shear test have been done using both the original damage formulation and the new interface element technique and are compared here.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The full test results on which the analysis is based have been published in reference 2 and are only briefly summarised here.

A single-lap shear specimen design, optimised to achieve a uniform shear stress over the central failure plane and minimal normal stresses under dynamic loading was tested in a compressive split Hopkinson bar apparatus. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the specimen

design and loading. Inset is a photograph of the failure plane obtained with the two parts of the specimen (separated after removal from the loading bars for clarity). The specimen was manufactured from carbon fibre/epoxy (T300/914) using unidirectional pre-preg tape in a cross-ply (0/90°) layup. Although a range of strain rates was tested, a single test at ~680/s has been chosen for comparison with the finite element analysis.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram showing loading mechanism and detail of failed specimen from testing in reference 2

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Model setup

The single-lap test has been modelled in the explicit finite element code LS-Dyna. This takes account of the dynamic stress wave propagation and is therefore suitable for the high strain rates applied here. Figure 2 shows the dimensions, mesh and boundary conditions of the model. Eight noded solid elements were used with a plane of symmetry on the centre-line. It was found to be necessary to model the input and output bars of the Hopkinson bar apparatus in order to correctly model the stress wave propagation and hence the dynamic stress state without spurious oscillations. A simplified rectangular cross sectional geometry was used instead of the circular cross section in the real case.

Figure 2 Finite element model showing dimensions and boundary conditions

The single-lap specimen itself was modelled with homogenised properties for the plies located away from the failure plane and on a ply by ply basis in the region between the two notch tips where failure occurred as shown in Figure 3. Material properties were taken from reference 2.

Figure 3 Detail of specimen dimensions and mesh

Original damage formulation – solid element based

The finite element model presented in reference 2 was revised to take advantage of increased computing power with a refined mesh and the inclusion of the input and output bars as described above. The delamination failure model is the same as that used in the original analysis (imbedded in LS-Dyna as material 22) is shown in Equation 1 and is based on that presented by Brewer and Legace⁴.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{31}}{S_{31}}\right)^2 \geq I \quad (1)$$

Where Z_f is direct through thickness strength, S_{23} and S_{31} are through-thickness shear strengths.

When the stress state in a given solid element exceeds the right hand side of the equation the element is deemed to have failed and the moduli are degraded accordingly. This is done over a very short period of time rather than instantaneously to overcome numerical instabilities.

Previous work² showed a stress concentration localised in a single element in the notch radius region. This indicates the presence of a stress singularity and further refinement of the mesh will result in increasingly greater stress predictions. Figure 4 shows six mesh densities used to obtain results for the solid element based delamination failure criterion. Additionally shown

in Figure 4e are the elemental XZ shear stresses which highlights the stress concentration in a single element at the end of the notch tip radius.

Mesh (a) uses only 1 element through the thickness of each ply as was done for the previous model in reference 2. Mesh (b) is refined in the in-plane X direction and mesh (c) is additionally refined in the in-plane Y direction. Mesh (d) is the same in-plane mesh as (a) but uses 3 elements through the thickness of each ply to better fit the curvature of the notch. Mesh (e) and (f) follow the same in-plane refinements as (b) and (c).

Figure 4 (a)-(f) Detail of specimen notch tip showing different mesh densities used

Revised damage formulation – interface element based

An interface element has been developed and implemented in LS-Dyna³. This 1D element connects two coincident nodes between adjacent solid elements and forms the basis for the delamination failure prediction. Initially its behaviour is linear elastic until a yield stress is reached. After this the stress in the element is reduced linearly to zero such that the total energy absorbed is equal to the fracture energy of the nodal area of the surface it represents. Figure 5a shows the traction displacement behaviour of the element in a single mode.

Figure 5 Interface element traction/displacements and locations within the single-lap specimen model

Since delamination failure is driven by a combination of shear and direct stress the facility for mixed mode behaviour needs to be implemented in the interface element. Equation 2 shows the linear interaction between mode I and mode II fracture energies to determine the ultimate failure of an element. This is illustrated graphically in Figure 5b.

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}}\right) + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right) \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

Since the single-lap shear test has been designed to study shear failure only the failure is mode II dominated though there is some interaction with compressive stresses as will be discussed later. Figure 5c shows the location of the interface elements within the single-lap specimen at the interfaces between the plies.

The interface material parameters of T300/914 are derived from references 5, 6 and 7 and are shown in Table 1. SY is the critical yield stress for initiation of damage progression in the normal and shear directions.

G_{IC} (N/mm)	G_{IIC} (N/mm)	SY_1 (MPa)	SY_{12} (MPa)	E (GPa)	G (GPa)
0.18	0.57	94	75	4.2	1.5

Table 1 Material parameters of interface elements

RESULTS

Original damage formulation

The average shear stress in the failure plane, which is derived by dividing the X direction output force (measured in the output bar) by the area of the failure plane, is used to describe the model response under dynamic loading. The six mesh patterns shown in Figure 4 are respectively applied to the single-lap specimen model in Figure 3. When the original solid element based delamination model is adopted, the numerical shear response as a function of time of the six models is obtained and compared in Figure 6. This shows that the simulated results are severely influenced by the mesh density, especially the X and Z directions.

Figure 6 Average shear stress vs. time for the six meshes shown in Figure 4 with solid element based failure

Revised damage formulation

When the revised interface element based delamination model is adopted, the shear responses of the models with the six mesh densities are obtained in the similar way as above and compared in Figure 7. The results can be seen to be nearly independent of the mesh pattern. The model with interface elements inserted is therefore more effective in simulating the failure response of the specimen under the given experimental loading conditions.

Figure 7 Average shear stress vs. time for the six meshes shown in Figure 4 with interface element based failure

The results shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 have not thus far been compared with the experimental result which was somewhat higher than all of the results presented at 77 MPa. A parametric study was undertaken to investigate the influence of the input parameters on results from the interface element model (mesh (e)). Results from this are shown in Table 2. Whilst there is some variation in the input parameters reported in the available literature it was felt that the large changes required to alter the predicted apparent shear strength indicated a deficiency in the model.

	Experimental Result	Baseline Interface Element Model	(-25%) SY_{12}	(+25%) SY_{12}	(-25%) G_{IIC}	(+25%) G_{IIC}
Failure Stress (MPa)	77.00	56.78	45.81	62.11	51.54	60.43

Table 2 Parametric study of the influence of interface element properties

Effect of compression stress

In the experimental results it was noted that the specimens failed slightly away from the centre-line on a plane consistent with the shear stress concentration. In the numerical analysis this was the predicted failure location for both the original and revised model. Unlike the test, two failure planes (shown in Figure 8) were predicted, progressing from the stress concentration at either end of the specimen. A more detailed investigation of the out of plane direct stress in the interface elements prior to failure on these planes indicates a region of compressive stress at the point of initiation. Figure 8c shows a normalised distribution of the stress along the two predicted failure planes with a minimum of -45.2MPa being reached just prior to failure.

Figure 8 Typical Y direction stress distribution in the model before failure

It is known that compressive stress can improve the delamination threshold and an attempt to take account of this was introduced into the interface element failure algorithm by combining Equation 1 and with the Puck Criteria⁸ for delamination initiation and Equation 2 with the empirically based formula for mode II fracture energy in Reference 9. A set of modified failure criteria are proposed to study the effect of compression on the predicted failure stress.

Failure Initiation Criterion:

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle}{Z_{33}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}^2 + \tau_{23}^2}{(S + \eta_1 \langle -\sigma_{33} \rangle)^2} \right) \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

Failure Propagation Criterion:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} \right) + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}(1 + \eta_2 \langle -\sigma_{33} \rangle)} \right) \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

Where

$$\langle X \rangle = \begin{cases} X, & X > 0 \\ 0, & X < 0 \end{cases}$$

In some publications^{8,10} the parameter η_1 in Equation 3 is understood as playing a role similar to an internal material friction parameter. Therefore, the original value of η_1 is taken as the friction coefficient from reference 11, i.e. $\eta_1=0.45$. The factor η_2 in Equation 4 is an empirical parameter determined experimentally and here the value of $\eta_2=0.02$ from reference¹² is used.

The new criteria above have been applied to the interface element based models. The dynamic shear response of the modified interface element models are obtained in the similar way as before and compared with those of the baseline interface element model and the experimental result in Figure 9. Firstly the revised failure initiation criterion (Equation 3) was implemented in isolation and this was then combined with the revised propagation (Equation 4).

Figure 9 Shear response of baseline and modified interface element models

The curves show that the strengthening effect of compressive stress on both the shear strength and G_{IIC} has an obvious influence on the simulation output. The model that considers the improvement of both shear strength and G_{IIC} gives much better result than the one that only considers the reinforcement of shear strength.

Though the improved model gives better result than the baseline interface element model, its predicted failure stress is still lower than experimental value. When a higher value of 0.8 is used for η_l , the improved model gives a response which is very close to the experimental result. This improvement suggests that friction might not be the only strengthening effect of compression on the delamination threshold.

DISCUSSION

The model with interface elements at the potential failure surface can effectively reduce the stress gradient and avoid the mesh dependency problems seen in the solid element based failure model. Further studies on the factors that result in the difference between predicted response and experimental results can therefore be undertaken.

Many publications on mixed-mode failure of composite laminates consider the interactive influence of tensile and shear stress. Some of them include studies on the strengthening effect of compressive stress on the shear strength, but few consider the influence of compressive strength on the Mode II fracture energy G_{IIC} . The preliminary study on the relationship of G_{IIC} and σ_{33} in the model shows that the increased G_{IIC} level can increase the apparent failure stress of the single-lap specimen significantly.

The coefficient η_l of compression on shear strength is usually said to play a role similar to an internal material friction parameter, but the study shows the value of η_l should be much higher than the actual friction coefficient. The effect of friction appears to only partly explain the observed increase in the final failure stress of the specimen in the presence of high through-thickness compressive stresses.

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